

USE OF ICT IN MATHEMATICS LESSONS

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The process of information, which today has covered all aspects of the life of modern society, has several priority areas, which, of course, include the information of education. It is the fundamental basis for the global rationalization of human intellectual activity through the use of information and communication technologies (hereinafter referred to as ICT). Information technologies have become an integral part of society and have an impact on learning processes and the education system as a whole.

The question of the use of ICT in the classroom, each teacher decides for himself. But let's first understand what is ICT? First of all it is: our computers, without which our existence;

– these are Internet resources that make it possible to use the possibilities of multi libraries and the worldwide Internet;

– these are interactive whiteboards with a lot of possibilities: to write, draw, plot, etc.;

– these are educational sites where you can find tests and tasks for olympiads in any subject, and take advanced courses

qualifications and many other opportunities; – these are also various demo versions, tests, tests.

But all this will give a result in the learning process when our students and students themselves work with these technologies.

It is no secret that it is difficult to keep students' attention for one hour and twenty minutes, especially when it comes to the subject of mathematics, because there is an increase in mental load, this makes us think about how to maintain students' interest in the subject being studied, their activity throughout lesson. In this regard, searches are underway for new effective teaching methods and such methodological techniques that would activate the thought of students, would stimulate them to independently acquire knowledge.

It is also necessary to make sure that each student works actively and enthusiastically in the lessons, and use this as a starting point for the emergence and development of curiosity, deep cognitive interest. That is why ICT is of interest and is being actively implemented in practice. It is known that according to research data, 25% of the material heard, 33% of what is seen, 50% of what is seen and heard, 75% of the material remains in the memory of a person if the student is involved in active actions in the learning process. ICTs make it possible to make the most of the educational process and their use in teaching is extremely effective.

Therefore, the capabilities of the computer are used in subject education in the following ways:

- use of additional material;
- use of diagnostic and control materials;
- improving the quality of visibility and accessibility in the presentation of material through the use of presentations in the classroom;

– performance of home, independent and creative tasks; – use of a computer for calculations, plotting graphs;

– formation of information competence of students, etc.

the ability to obtain information from various sources, including electronic ones.

The software of educational disciplines is very diverse: textbook programs, simulator programs, dictionaries, reference books, encyclopedias, video tutorials, libraries of electronic visual aids.

ICT solves the problem of individualization of learning. Usually students, who learn the teacher's explanations more slowly than their comrades, are embarrassed to raise their hands and ask questions. Having the same computer as a partner, they can repeat the material many times at their own pace and control the degree of assimilation. The use of color, graphics, animation, sound, all modern means, ICT allows you to recreate the real environment of the activity.

The use of ICT in the educational process allows you to conduct lessons:

– at a high aesthetic and emotional level (music, animation);

- provides visibility;

– attracts a large amount of didactic material;

– increases the amount of work performed in the lesson;

– provides a high degree of differentiation of training (individual approach to the student, using multi-level tasks).

ICT justifies itself in all respects: – improves the quality of knowledge;

promotes the student in general development;

– helps to overcome difficulties, brings joy to the life of a student;

– creates favorable conditions for a better mutual understanding of the teacher and the student and their cooperation in the educational process.

This technology contributes to: activation of students' cognitive activity; development of thinking, mathematical logic; orientation of students' mental activity towards search and research.

The issue of the advisability of using ICT became resolved after several trial lessons. It can be seen that students have a genuine interest in working on a computer and an increased interest in the study of mathematics. And our goal is to educate a person who is able to independently make decisions, adapt to new conditions, be smart, and find the necessary information. You can use ICT at any stage of the lesson: when studying new material, consolidating, in general lessons, when repeating. The main task is to properly organize the work of students.

At each specific lesson, certain presentations are used. You can use presentations and mini-slides that the teacher creates himself, and you can also use ready-made lessons that can be found on the Internet. In lessons with ICT, the use of such features as animation, colors, sound keeps students' attention. At such lessons, the interest in the subject is increased among the students. They enthusiastically answer the questions of the teacher, perform independent work with subsequent verification, and give themselves preliminary marks.

The inclusion of information and computer technologies in the course of the lesson makes the process of teaching mathematics interesting and entertaining, creates a cheerful, working mood among students, and facilitates overcoming difficulties in mastering educational material. However, it is not a fact that the use of ICT in the classroom makes it possible to master mathematics “easily and

happily”. There are no easy paths to science. But it is necessary to use every opportunity so that students study with interest, so that most of them experience and realize the attractive aspects of mathematics, its possibilities in improving mental abilities, in overcoming difficulties.

Since electronic media contain educational, visual information, simulators, diagnostic and control tools, they can be used to form a figurative representation of the object under study and for individual work with students.

When using ICT to develop students' skills on the topic and control carried out using this technology, the quality of their knowledge is higher than with traditional methods.

By organizing work with tests (in electronic form) in the classroom and outside of school hours, teachers form the main “information” competencies in students, and for many, they are the most relevant today and will be needed in the future.

Information technologies increase the information content of the lesson, the effectiveness of teaching, give the lesson dynamism and expressiveness. The result of the introduction of ICT in the educational process is the positive dynamics of changes in students' motivation. Using a computer in the classroom is not a tribute to fashion, not a way to shift the many-sided creative work of a teacher onto the “shoulders” of a computer. And only one of the means to intensify the educational process, activate cognitive activity, increase student motivation and increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

Bibliography

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